

Edge-Preserving Generative Adversarial Networks for Enhanced Underwater Image Restoration

Additional code resources and implementation details for our work, “*Edge-Preserving Generative Adversarial Networks for Enhanced Underwater Image Restoration*,” are available in the following GitHub repository. This repository includes supplementary scripts, model configurations, and experimental materials that support and extend the methods presented in the paper.

Github link: <https://github.com/plawangshishugit/EPGAN>